

Use of Phenolic Acids in the Detection, Separation and Estimation of Metals. Part V. Separation of Copper from Cadmium and their subsequent Estimations.

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When gallic acid and sodium or ammonium acetate are added to neutral or faintly acidic solutions of copper or cadmium salts, a voluminous chocolate brown precipitate is obtained in the case of copper, which is quantitative and in the case of cadmium no precipitate is formed (Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 631). These reactions have been studied further.

The precipitate with copper appears to be a definite compound, as on gently heating it gives a constant percentage of pure cupric oxide. The precipitate is soluble in mineral acids and in large excess of acetic acid. On heating it with sodium hydroxide, cuprous oxide is formed.

The precipitate is not of much use in estimating copper, as it is difficult to filter it through a Gooch crucible. The estimation is however much quicker, if the precipitate is dried, incinerated and weighed as CuO. This method is quite satisfactory in determining copper in presence of cadmium.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Faintly acidic solutions of copper and cadmium nitrates are separately made and copper and cadmium estimated by standard methods. Each c. c. of the copper and cadmium solutions contained 0.09883 and 0.09936 g. of Cu and Cd respectively.

A measured volume of the copper nitrate solution is taken in a beaker, diluted with water to a considerable volume, and excess of a 10% solution of ammonium acetate is added. The solution is

heated nearly to boiling and a freshly prepared saturated solution of gallic acid (1 %) is added drop by drop until the precipitation is complete. The voluminous precipitate is allowed to settle and filtered. The precipitate adhering to the side of the beaker is washed out into the filter with warm 2 % NH_4NO_3 solution. The precipitate is dried in the steam-oven (at higher temperature the substance attacks the filter) and ignited cautiously. The crucible is heated first gently over a low flame and then strongly for a few minutes when the precipitate is transformed to cupric oxide.

TABLE I.

Vol. of Cu soln. after dilution (c.c.).	Vol. of 10 % ammonium acetate soln. (c.c.).	Vol. of 1 % gallic acid soln. (c.c.).	CuO found (g.).	CuO present (g.).
25	15	25	0.1231	} 0.1237
35	..	20	0.1236	
25	20	25	0.1234	
60	25	30	0.2468	0.2474
20	2	5	0.0244	} 0.02474
40	3	..	0.0246	
15	* 2+5 c.c. 8 % NH_4NO_3 soln.	3	0.0122	} 0.01237
25	* 3+5 c.c. 8 % NH_4NO_3 soln.	..	0.0121	

* Addition of ammonium nitrate helps coagulation of the precipitate.

Separation and Estimation of Copper and Cadmium when present together.

Measured volumes of copper and cadmium solutions are taken and as before, copper is precipitated by ammonium acetate and gallic acid. The copper precipitate is then washed by decantation with hot 2 % ammonium nitrate solution to free it from cadmium, which is tested in the filtrate by sulphuretted hydrogen. The copper precipitate is then dried and as before estimated as cupric oxide. In the filtrate, cadmium is first precipitated as cadmium sulphide, filtered, washed well with sulphuretted hydrogen water and estimated as cadmium sulphate. In this way with

different proportions of copper and cadmium solutions several estimations are made, which are given below.

TABLE II

Vol. of soln. containing Cu & Cd after dilution. (c.c.).	Vol. of ammonium acetate soln. (c.c.).	Vol. of 1% gallic acid (c.c.).	CuO found (g.).	CuO present (g.).	CdSO ₄ found (g.).	CdSO ₄ present (g.).
45	15	25	·1239	·1237	·1840	·1843
35	20	35	·1241	·1237	·1845	·1843
40	25	40	·2488	·2474	·1835	·1843
30	25	30	·1235	·1237	·3684	·3686
40	10	5	·0248	·0247	·3681	·3686
50	15	10	·0249	·0247	·3684	·3686
40	25	40	·2477	·2474	·0368	·0368
45	30	35	·2482	·2474	·0369	·0368

In all the cases the cupric oxide and the cadmium sulphate are tested for possible contaminations of cadmium and copper respectively. In every case negative results are obtained.

Conclusion.

This method of separation and estimation of copper and cadmium can be claimed to be rapid and accurate. In the case of copper, this is also a more rapid and accurate gravimetric method; small amounts of copper can also be estimated gravimetrically by this method, as the precipitate obtained is very voluminous.

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